

River plastic retention and export across Europe

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Abstract

Rivers play a central role in the global distribution of plastic pollution. Despite recent research showing that the majority of plastic is not transported to sea, most plastic transport models have not explicitly included plastic retention in rivers. We propose a new model to quantify micro- and macroplastic retention on land and in rivers, and export towards the sea. Of the 3.55 Mt year⁻¹ of plastics emitted to the environment, only 0.1% of microplastics and 0.5% of macroplastics are exported from the river outlet. This results in 16.9 kt year⁻¹ of microplastic and 3.2 kt year⁻¹ export. Rivers act as temporary sinks, retaining 259.1 kt year⁻¹ of microplastics (5.3%) and 67.4 kt year⁻¹ of macroplastics (2.5%), while the greatest proportion of plastic remains on land. Although large basin size and high plastic emissions to the environment characterize high absolute micro- and macroplastic retention and export, large basin

size is a weaker predictor for retention and export per capita. By aggregating ranks for plastic export and retention, we provide a new and comprehensive outlook on the most polluting rivers of Europe. This work provides crucial baseline estimates for plastic pollution in light of missing plastic reduction quotas to guide future prioritization and assessment of mitigation actions.

Introduction

An estimated 52.1 million metric tonnes of plastic waste was released into the environment worldwide in 2020,¹ and is predicted to increase in the coming years.² Both micro- (< 0.5 cm) and macroplastics (> 0.5 cm) have been shown to pose significant risks to ecosystems and organisms, with negative effects including entrapment, endocrine disruption, and bioaccumulation in high trophic levels.^{3,4} Rivers play a central role in the transport of plastic pollution, facilitating their movement downstream from their source or retaining them temporarily along the river trajectory.^{5,6} To better understand these processes, rivers are monitored for plastic pollution.^{7,8} Beyond direct monitoring, models can provide insights into the fate of plastic and how they are transported or temporarily retained in river basins across wider spatial and temporal scales.

Large-scale modelling of plastic transport can identify rivers which are highly polluted across a large spatial scale. Various large-scale models for plastic transport have been developed, including Lebreton et al.⁹, Schmidt et al.¹⁰, Meijer et al.¹¹, Stokal et al.¹² and Nakayama and Osako¹³. These export models combine population density and mismanaged plastic waste estimates with river basin characteristics to estimate plastic export to sea. These models only quantify plastic export, and overlook the importance of quantifying plastic retention in the river despite recent findings showing that the majority of plastics are likely retained within the river system.^{6,11,14} Another limitation to previous modelling studies is that many models are calibrated with limited data. While macroplastic export models have undergone sufficient model calibration, where modelled estimates are compared

to field measurements (e.g., Meijer et al.¹¹), steps for data harmonisation are under-specified, limiting reproducibility. Microplastic export models remain partially uncalibrated^{10,15,16} due to the complexity and restrictions in microplastic field measurements. Therefore, our modelling approach includes thorough data harmonization and model calibration, allowing for the quantification of plastic retention and export from rivers.

Here, we present a European high resolution model for micro- and macroplastics export and retention for 8696 river basins. We express our model results in absolute and per capita terms to show the total impact of plastic in river systems, and to assess the local leakage risks. We incorporate the latest research in plastic mobilisation to explore micro- and macroplastic transport and retention processes across European rivers. Overland transport processes include meteorological drivers^{17,18} and land-use-related mechanisms,¹⁹ while river transport is shaped by riverbank friction processes,²⁰ and artificial infrastructures.²¹ We used recent plastic field measurements (i.e., González-Fernández et al.⁸, Schöneich-Argent et al.²², Piehl et al.²³, Pol et al.²⁴), to strengthen the quality in data harmonisation for calibration. Our research provides valuable insights into quantifying the proportion of plastic that is retained on land, in the river and exported to the river outlet. This information can be used to provide guidance for designing, implementing and evaluating plastic pollution reduction measures.

Methodology

Model approach

Our model estimates independently the mass of microplastics ($1\mu\text{m}$ - 5mm) and macroplastics ($> 5\text{mm}$) that is retained on land, retained within rivers, or exported to the outlet for 8696 European rivers (see S1 in SI). To estimate yearly fluxes, we apply a spatially probabilistic model, developed by building on the framework proposed by Meijer et al.¹¹ at a 3×3 arc-second resolution (approximately 100 m at the equator). We calculate the likelihood of plastics being transported from mismanaged sources across land, into rivers, and ultimately

exported to the river outlet, following flow direction (Figure 1). We define "export to outlet" in our model as plastic that is transported to the river outlet boundary, without considering what is transported further to sea. Estuarine dynamics are not included in this model due to the complexity of tidal and retention processes, a research area still in its early developmental stages.⁵ Estimates are provided for 2015 due to the availability of input data.^{25,26}

Figure 1: A schematic of the spatially probabilistic model. Land cells are shown in green and river cells in blue, with arrows showing the direction of travel. Three sources of plastic, tire wear particles and mismanaged micro- and macroplastic waste are directly introduced onto land, while plastic from WWTPs directly enter the river system. All plastic sources which enter the river are then either accumulated along the river trajectory or transported to the outlet of the river system.

Model formulation

We determine three key temporary sinks of plastic for a single annual cycle, retention on land, retention in the river and export to the outlet (Figure 1), in a closed system. Cleaning or removal processes are not incorporated to provide an estimation of plastic pollution before cleaning. We, therefore, estimate the upper bounds of plastic retention across land and rivers, revealing the spatial patterns and magnitude of plastic pollution. The model formulation is described in detail below.

Plastic mobilisation on land

Human activity on land is a key source of plastic.²⁷ We account for two key processes, transport due to surface runoff, and wind to quantify plastic transport across land. By estimating the probability (0-1) of plastic mobilisation due to wind, $P(W)_n$, and surface runoff, $P(S)_n$, independently, we determine the fraction of plastic that is mobilised on land, $P(L)_n$, at each grid cell, n . This is given by:

$$P(L)_n = P(W \cup S)_n = \min((P(W)_n + P(S)_n), 1) \quad (1)$$

The independent processes reflect the experimental set-up of Mellink et al.¹⁸ which explored the effect of aeolian and pluvial processes on plastic mobilisation separately. Mellink et al.¹⁸ showed larger wind speeds increase the shear stress that is exerted on micro- and macroplastics, increasing mobilisation. Plastic mobilisation from wind, $P(W)_n$ (0-1), is further affected by the interaction of the driving force of wind, w_n (m s^{-1}), and resisting forces, land friction, lf_n ($(-\log_{10} \text{ m})$), and slope, s_n ($^\circ$), such that:

$$P(W)_n = \min((c_w \cdot w_n) \cdot (c_{lf_w} \cdot lf_n) \cdot (c_{s_w} \cdot s_n), 1) \quad (2)$$

where, the probability of plastic mobilisation due to wind for each grid cell (n), is between 0-1. To quantify land friction we use the CORINE land cover classes²⁸ and apply friction values to each corresponding land class given by Dörenkämper et al.²⁹. Friction values from Dörenkämper et al.²⁹, otherwise defined as roughness length (z_0), used in a wind atlas generation, were applied to the CORINE land classes. Friction values were then transformed using $(-\log_{10})$ resulting in inverse friction values, with a minimum value of 0.1, to prevent zero mobilisation values. (see Table S1 in the SI).

Similarly, we determine that the probability of mobilization by surface runoff is given by the combined effect of the driving force, surface runoff, sr_n (L h^{-1}),³⁰ and resisting forces,

land friction, lf_n $((-)\log_{10} \text{ m})^{28,29}$ and slope, s_n ($^\circ$). While Meijer et al.¹¹ uses rainfall as a predictor for plastic mobilisation on land, we instead employ surface runoff as an explanatory factor. Research suggests that plastic mobilisation can only occur if there is sufficient surface runoff, where positively buoyant plastic can be lifted and mobilised.^{17,18} The combined effect of surface runoff, land-friction and slope is given by:

$$P(S)_n = \min((c_{sr} \cdot sr_n) \cdot (c_{lf_{sr}} \cdot lf_n) \cdot (c_{s_{sr}} \cdot s_n), 1) \quad (3)$$

The probability of plastic mobilisation due to surface runoff, $P(S)$, for each grid cell (n) , bound within the range 0–1. The same input of land-friction and slope is used, however, distinct coefficients are applied to each input (c_{lf_s} and $c_{s_{sr}}$) to account for the combined resisting effect with surface runoff. Coefficient values can be seen in Table S3, in the SI. Monthly averaged data for surface runoff and wind speed is used to calculate the average surface runoff and wind speed for the period of 2014 - 2016,³⁰ to match the availability of mismanaged plastic waste.²⁵ By accounting for wind, surface runoff, slope and land-friction, we determine the probability of plastic mobilisation from one grid cell to the next, $P(L)_n$. To find the probability that plastic is transported across land, we find the product of $P(L)_n$ for each grid cell along the overland transport pathway to the closest river cell, $P(pL)$. This is given by:

$$P(pL)_{(n,n_0)} = \prod_{s=n_0}^n P(L)_s \quad (4)$$

where the transport pathway is the product of the probability of transport on land, $P(L)$, from the closest river cell $s = n_0$, to the further in-land cell of interest, $s = n$. The transport pathway is given by using flow direction, a digital elevation model (DEM)³¹ and the “Flow Distance” ArcGIS tool. These determine the local drainage direction across land.

Plastic mobilisation in the river

Plastic in the river system is affected by the driving force, discharge, and resisting forces, riverbank friction, Strahler order and dams. Discharge is commonly used in models,^{11,15} where an increase in discharge leads to an increase in transport capacity. Strahler order is a proxy for river width given that smaller-order streams with narrower cross-sections can experience greater resisting force between riverine plastics and the riverbed.³² Cesarini and Scalici²⁰ found that the type of riverbank affects the entrapment of plastic along the river trajectory. The same friction values used for land friction²⁹ are used for riverbank friction, using the focal average of land friction of land cells surrounding a river cell. Finally, we account for dams,³³ as these have the potential to trap large quantities of plastic.^{34,35} We calculate the probability that plastic is mobilised in the river, $P(R)_n$ (0-1), by:

$$P(R)_n = \min(p + (c_d \cdot d_n) + (c_{bf} \cdot bf_n) + (c_{so} \cdot so_n), 1) \quad (5)$$

for each river cell, n . The first parameter, p , serves as an intercept term, indicating the expected probability of plastic transport in the river when contributing factors are zero. The additional additive effect of discharge, d_n ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$),³⁶ Strahler order, so_n , and riverbank friction, bf_n ($(-\log_{10} \text{ m})$), is then capped between 0-1. Due to limited knowledge on the proportion of plastic that is entrapped by dams, we cap mobilisation at 15% for those river cells.³⁷ We determine that the probability that plastic is transported from its river entry to the outlet of the river system, $P(pR)$, as:

$$P(pR)_{(n,n_0)} = \prod_{s=n_0}^n P(R)_s \quad (6)$$

where the pathway transport is the product of the probability of riverine transport $P(R)$, from the outlet cell, $s = n_0$ to the point of entry in the river, $s = n$. This pathway is generated using flow direction and the ArcGIS tool "Flow Length". To determine the

probability that plastic is transported from land to the river outlet, $P(O)$, we find the product of the probability of plastic being transported to the river system, $P(pL)$, and the probability that plastic is transported to the river outlet, $P(pR)$. This is given by:

$$P(O)_n = P(pL \cap pR)_n = P(pL)_n \cdot P(pR)_n \quad (7)$$

for each cell, n , in the catchment area, n .

Fate of plastic

For each cell in the river basin, n , we find the proportion of plastic that is exported to sea by calculating the product of the total input of plastic, i (kg year^{-1}), that enters the environment in a cell, n , and the probability of plastic export to sea $P(O)$. The total quantity of plastic that reaches the outlet of the river basin, E (kg year^{-1}), is found by aggregating at the individual cells in the river basin, by:

$$E_n = \sum_{s=n_0}^n (P(O)_s \times i_s) \quad (8)$$

for each basin, n . To find the total plastic export, all cells within the river basin are included (from n_0 to n). To quantify the total mass of plastic that is retained within the a river, Rr (kg year^{-1}), for each river basin, n , at a annual timescale we calculate:

$$Rr_n = \left(\sum_{s=n_0}^n (P(pL)_s \times i_s) \right) - E_n \quad (9)$$

Firstly, we calculated the total sum of proportion of plastic that enters the river system, $P(pL)$ (0-1), from what enters the environment, i (kg year^{-1}) for all cells (from n_0 to n). Secondly, we found the remainder of the mass of plastic stays within the river system, by subtracting the mass of plastic reached the outlet, E , for river basin, n . The total mass of plastic that is retained on land, Rl (kg year^{-1}), is given by the following mass balance

equation:

$$Rl_n = I_n - E_n - Rr_n \quad (10)$$

The mass of plastic that is exported, E (kg year^{-1}) and retained in the river, Rr (kg year^{-1}), are removed from the total mass of plastic that enters land, I (kg year^{-1}). The remaining total gives the mass of plastic that is retained on land, for each river basin, n .

Estimating plastic input

To quantify the transport and retention of plastic on land and in rivers, we estimate the mass of micro- and macroplastic that enters the environment as an input to the model. We account for one source of macroplastic, mismanaged macroplastic waste (MaPW, $2.45 \text{ Mt year}^{-1}$),²⁵ and three sources of microplastic inputs. These sources include, mismanaged plastics in the form of microplastics (MiPW, $0.02 \text{ Mt year}^{-1}$),³⁸ tire wear particles (TWP, $0.93 \text{ Mt year}^{-1}$)³⁹ and waste water treatment plants (WWTPs, 0.2 Mt year^{-1}).⁴⁰ A full description of the quantification of the sources of plastic is in S3 in the SI.

Calibration and validation

To calibrate and validate the model, field measurements in 29 rivers for microplastic transport and 36 rivers for macroplastic transport from existing literature were used. Field measurements were harmonised and extrapolated to yearly mass fluxes using a methodology from⁴¹ (see Table S4 and S5 in the SI). A calibration and validation ratio of 70%-30% was used, accounting for total plastic emission to land and maximum river discharge. Monte Carlo model runs were carried out (around 120 per run) to carry out the model calibration, using an initial predefined range of parameter values. Model performance was assessed using the r^2 by comparing modelled yearly plastic flux ($\log_{10} \text{ kg year}^{-1}$) and measured yearly plastic flux ($\log_{10} \text{ kg year}^{-1}$). By assessing the individual parameter effect on model output, parameter

ranges were refined, and a following seven Monte Carlo model runs were carried out in an iterative process. The remained field measurements were used to validate the performance of the best model run, which resulted in the highest r^2 from model calibration.

Data analysis

We express micro- and macroplastic retention and export in terms of absolute and normalised values for each river basin in Europe for 2015. To assess the characteristics of the most polluting rivers in terms of absolute and per capita estimates for river retention and export, we use a subset of the top 1% ($n = 87$) of rivers for each plastic fate. We further express the median export and retention (absolute and per capita) for each group of basin size classes, < 10 , $10 - 100$, $100 - 1000$ and $> 1000\text{km}^2$. To assess the overall level of pollution of a river basin, we assigned and aggregated river basins ranks for each of the four fates of plastic, micro- and macroplastic retention, and export. Spearman rank tests were also carried out to find the statistical relationship between two groups of ranks. We compare micro- and macroplastic export estimates for the largest 15 rivers of Europe to other large scale plastic export models. Macroplastic export estimates were compared to estimates from Lebreton et al.⁹, Schmidt et al.¹⁰, Meijer et al.¹¹, Strokhal et al.¹⁵ and microplastic export estimates were compared to those from Schmidt et al.¹⁰, Strokhal et al.¹⁵, Siegfried et al.¹⁶.

Results and discussion

Plastic export model performance

From model calibration, we find that our results for micro- and macroplastic transport corresponded well with field data, resulting in r^2 values of 0.68 for microplastics and 0.86 for macroplastics (Figure 2). Results of the model validation confirmed that the model was also able to predict the plastic transport in rivers which were not using in the calibration set (0.88 for microplastic transport and 0.79 for macroplastic transport).

Figure 2: Results from the model calibration and validation for a) micro- and b) macroplastic transport. River in the calibration are given in black and validation in red. Model performance estimates (r^2) are shown with model performance including outliers shown in brackets. A 1:1 line is also included, grey dashed lines to show one order of magnitude difference.

As a result of field measurement extrapolation and limitations in the model, several rivers were identified as being outliers and were removed from the model performance analysis. These modelled values differed from the extrapolated field values by more than two orders of magnitude. We find that with the inclusion of outliers, the model performance for macroplastic export (r^2 of 0.53) was higher than that for microplastic export (r^2 of 0.2). While field measurement extrapolation uncertainty stems from field technique limitation (e.g., limited size range coverage and duration), model uncertainty stems from our incomplete understanding of the sources of plastics in the environment, transport and retention processes, and model formulation. These uncertainties highlight the importance of comparing model results with field measurements and ensuring transparency in estimating plastic transport. Overall, however, the model calibration demonstrates strong performance, providing confidence in its ability to capture the most relevant transport dynamics.

Less plastic is transported to the river outlet than previous estimates

We estimate that a very small proportion of plastic that is released to the environment is transported to the river outlets (Figure 3). Of the 3.56 Mt year⁻¹ of mismanaged plastic that is produced in Europe each year, only 20.12 kt year⁻¹ (0.14% of all microplastic and 0.45% of all macroplastic) is exported to the outlet of all rivers (Figure 3a). The proportion of plastic that is transported to the river outlet deviates from the research work of Meijer et al.¹¹. Meijer et al.¹¹ stated that 2% of all mismanaged macroplastic is exported to the river outlet. Estimating the total mass of plastic that is transported to the river outlet of the four main seas that border Europe (North East Atlantic, Mediterranean, Baltic and Black sea), we find that the North East Atlantic receives the highest mass of plastic waste from rivers (9.08 kt year⁻¹). The Mediterranean sea follows, with an export of 6.93 kt year⁻¹. The Baltic sea and Black sea are estimated to export 3.20 kt year⁻¹ and 0.90 kt year⁻¹, respectively.

Figure 3: a. Range in the proportion (%) of micro- and macroplastic that is retained on land, retained in the river system, and exported to the river outlet.; b. We present the total mass of plastic export and retention in river and land. The total export of micro- and macroplastics are 16.9 and 3.20 kt year⁻¹, with river retention totalling 159.1 and 67.4 kt year⁻¹, respectively. The total quantity of macroplastic retention on land equates to 2374.6 kt year⁻¹, while total microplastic retention on land is 934.2 kt year.

Results from the model show that rivers are an important temporary sink for plastics. We estimate that 9 times more microplastics ($159.1 \text{ kt year}^{-1}$), and 21 times more macroplastics ($67.4 \text{ kt year}^{-1}$) are retained in all river systems, compared to the total mass that is exported (Figure 3b). These findings are also supported by van Emmerik et al.⁶ which state that rivers are important for the retention of plastic. The final and largest proportion of plastic is retained on land (94.0% of all microplastics and 96.9% of all macroplastics). This results in a total retention of $0.93 \text{ Mt year}^{-1}$ of microplastics and $2.37 \text{ Mt year}^{-1}$ macroplastics on land (Figure 3b). Model results show a large inter-basin variability in Figure 3a, where the proportion of plastic export and river retention range from 0 - 100% across basins. Basins with a high proportion of micro- and macroplastic export which are considered outliers in Figure 3a ($>25\%$), are characterised by a small basin size, with the largest share of plastic emissions entering land close to the river outlet. Small basin size, and location of plastic emission to land also drives the outlier for river and land retention. Further understanding the characteristics of rivers which results in either a high or low retention and export can offer us useful insights into understanding the overall pollution level of a river system.

Comparing transport to outlet estimates with other model estimates

Modelled export estimates vary greatly between models (Figure 4), with differing by as much as 2-4 orders of magnitude. We find that the majority of our main river estimates (67% of macroplastic and 73% of microplastic) fall within minimum and maximum of other results. In addition to variations in model set-up, variations in model estimates stem from differences in quantifying plastic input and model calibration. Our model, Meijer et al.¹¹ and Stokal et al.¹⁵ use estimates from Lebreton and Andrady²⁵ for MaPW, while Lebreton et al.⁹ and Siegfried et al.¹⁶ use different estimates. For microplastic export, our model integrates three microplastic sources (MiPW, TWP, and WWTPs). Schmidt et al.¹⁰ accounts solely for MiPW, while, Stokal et al.¹⁵ accounts for WWTPs and MiPW, and Siegfried et al.¹⁶

accounts solely for point sources (WWTPs). Regarding calibration, our model and Meijer et al.¹¹ use field data for the Rhine for macroplastic model calibration.⁴² While Meijer et al.¹¹ extrapolated field measurements estimating an observation-based yearly plastic transport of 38 t year⁻¹, we estimate 2-34 t year⁻¹. Prior modelling efforts for microplastic export have lacked the extensive calibration methodology implemented here, due to prior reduced data availability.^{9,10,15,16} Transparency in quantifying plastic sources and data handling for model calibration are, therefore, crucial when comparing model estimates.

We find that models with a higher resolution are better able to account for the majority of plastic export, compared to low resolution models. We estimate that 239 (2.8%) river systems contribute 80% of macroplastic export, while 141 (1.6%) rivers accounts for 80% of microplastics export. Selecting only European river, Meijer et al.¹¹ estimated that 188 (7.4%) rivers contribute to 80% of plastic waste at the river outlet, while Lebreton et al.⁹ estimates 18 (0.4%), and Schmidt et al.¹⁰ only 11 (0.8%). Coarser models^{9,10} may underestimate or fail to model plastic transport in small river basins, which can have a substantial impact on total plastic export due to their proximity with the coastal region.⁴³ Accurately estimating the mass of plastic reaching river outlets requires accounting for the flux contributed by small drainage basins, which requires a model with high resolution.

High absolute export and retention estimates are associated with large basin size and large plastic emission to land

High absolute estimates for plastic fate (top 1%) are strongly associated with large basin areas (Figure 5). This relationship is particularly pronounced for high retention estimates, with the median basin size being 114 and 398 times greater than the median basin size for macro- and microplastic retention. These results are supported in Table 1 where the largest size class (> 1000 km²) consistently shows the highest estimates across all absolute estimates for micro- and macroplastic retention and export. Schmidt et al.¹⁰, also report that large river basins receiving substantial plastic inputs resulting in a large plastic export. Despite

Figure 4: The range in micro- and macroplastic export values from various large scale plastic transport models for the 15 largest river of Europe.

the association of large basin size with high absolute estimates, rivers with the highest 20 estimates for macroplastic export are medium coastal basins (88 km²) (Figure 5), being only three times greater than the median basin size for all basins. This is consistent with Lebreton et al.⁹ and González-Fernández et al.⁸, who show that coastal basins often have high export efficiency. These coastal regions are characterised by intense plastic inputs to the environment, enabling even smaller basins to become disproportionately large macroplastic exporters.

High absolute micro- and macroplastic retention and export (top 1%) are also characterised with large plastic entry to the environment. The median emission of plastic to land is more than 1,100 and 6,100 times greater for high plastic retention for micro- and macroplastics, while the median emission is more than 260 and 1,600 greater for micro- and macroplastic export, compared to the median emission to land at a basin level. Results from Strokhal et al.¹² and Meijer et al.¹¹, also reflect these results, with basins characterised by large emissions of plastic from dense urbanization in high plastic export. While absolute estimates are vital in showing the total impact of plastic on the environment, which can

Figure 5: The spatial distribution of rivers with various levels of absolute and per capita plastic export and retention. Colours represent percentile classes of estimates plastic export and retention, with darker red shades indicating higher percentiles. Percentile classes are given in the SI (Table S6). Individual absolute estimates for the highest 20 rivers are also displayed.

be used for guiding regional and national mitigation strategies and policies, these estimates often disproportionately show the effect of extensively populated areas. By accounting for population density it is possible to explore plastic pollution patterns across countries, by isolating population intensity from basin size. This ensures that policies can be developed fairly by ensuring that responsibility is balanced.

High absolute micro- and macroplastic retention and export (top 1%) are also characterised with large plastic entry to the environment. The median emission of plastic to land is more than 1,100 and 6,100 times greater for high plastic retention for micro- and macroplastics, while the median emission is more than 260 and 1,600 greater for micro- and macroplastic export, compared to the median emission to land at a basin level. These results

Table 1: The median absolute and per capita estimate for micro- and macroplastic export and retention based on basin size groups.

Basin size (km ²)	Macroplastic exp.		Microplastic exp.		Macroplastic ret.		Microplastic ret.	
	(kg)	(kg cap ⁻¹)						
< 10	0.8	0.16	2.5	0.6	0.5	0.08	16.1	4.01
10 – 100	5.0	0.3	1.7	0.1	17.5	0.9	64.1	4.95
100 – 1000	12.2	0.09	25.8	0.3	330	1.7	970	6.6
> 1000	90.7	0.03	2362	1.3	5349	2.0	25372	11.0

align with Strokal et al.¹² and Meijer et al.¹¹, who find that large emissions of plastic to land results in high plastic export. Absolute estimates are vital in understanding the total environmental impact of plastic on a river system and for guiding regional and national mitigation strategies and policies. However, high absolute plastic export and retention in large basins may disproportionately show the effect of extensively populated areas, due to the larger area available for inhabitants. By accounting for population density it is possible to explore plastic pollution patterns across countries, by isolating population intensity from basin size. This ensures that international policies can be developed fairly by ensuring that responsibility is balanced.

High per capita estimates are associated with a high quantity of mismanaged plastic

Large basin size is no longer a reliable predictor of high plastic export and retention when scaled by population density. For rivers with high plastic retention and export, the median surface area is comparable to the median basin size of all modelled basins (19.4 - 44.3 km²). Smaller basins tend to have a lower discharge which reduces the driving force of riverine transport, encouraging plastic retention.⁴⁴ Small coastal basins also often have large populations close to the river outlet which can promote a higher export efficiency,⁸ in addition to WWTPs promoting the direct transport of plastic to the river outlet. Despite this, when accounting for all river basins, we find that the largest basin size group (> 1000 km²) has the

Figure 6: The spatial distribution of rivers with various levels of plastic export and retention scaled by total population density. Percentile classes of a darker shade indicate higher percentile classes. These classes are given in the SI (Table S7). Individual estimates for the 20 highest export and retention scaled by population density are shown.

largest estimates for microplastic export and retention, and macroplastic retention (Table 1). We find that plastic pollution scaled by population density therefore highly depends on the context of mismanaged plastic.

Large inputs of plastic to the environment strongly drive high microplastic retention and macroplastic retention and export scaled by population density, while the location of WWTPs plays an important role in elevated estimates for microplastic export. High macro- and microplastic retention ($> 96^{th}$ percentile) is found primarily in south-east Europe, while basins with high microplastic retention (85 - 96^{th} percentile) are found in main, south and northern Europe (Figure 6). These variation are linked to sources of plastic with MaPW emissions dominating south-eastern Europe²⁵ and WWTP density dominating main, south

and northern Europe.²⁶ Surprisingly, basins with high microplastic export contribute only 1/7 of total microplastic emissions to land compared to all basins. These rivers have a single large point source (WWTPs) close to the river outlet and small population densities upstream which disproportionately affect per capita estimates. Since per capita estimates are more suited to informing large scale policy decisions, careful data interpretation is required to ensure that these distorted predictions are accounted for.

Aggregating plastic fate rankings provides a new look on river basin pollution

By applying an overall rank to each river system, we find that the most polluting rivers are Kurbağalı Dere, Vistula and Rhine (Table 2). We observe a large range in individual ranks for absolute micro- and macroplastic export and river retention (1-129). The river with the highest macroplastic export (Seyhan) and retention (Danube) and highest microplastic export (Thames), fall outside the top 10 most polluted rivers. With the quantification of plastic retention being overlooked in plastic transport models,^{11,15} we show that accounting for retention is very important when assessing the overall level of plastic pollution. Plastic export alone provides a skewed perception of riverine plastic pollution. The Vistula, Rhine, and West Oder, have higher retention ranks than their export ranks. These combined ranks can be used to identify the total environmental burden that each river system has.

Assessing the correlation between pairs of export and retention ranks for plastic pollution, we find a significant positive relationship for each pair of ranks ($p < 0.05$) (see S6 in the SI). The highest ρ value, from the Spearman's rank tests, was observed between macroplastic export rank and macroplastic river retention rank (0.793). Given that all Spearman's rank pairs showed a significant positive relationship, this indicates that a river with a high macroplastic export rank is likely to have a high microplastic export rank, and high macro- and microplastic river retention rank. While this positive correlation implies that information on one plastic fate has the potential to show the level of pollution of other fate,

it does not imply redundancy when assessing the final rank of a river. Stokal et al.¹⁵ states the same river system can differ greatly in micro- and macroplastics export. This is shown clearly in Table 2 for the river Elbe, which has a high ranking for microplastic export (3), yet a lower ranking for macroplastic export (266). This difference highlights the fact that while a high macroplastic export may often be paired with high microplastic export, variability between river systems requires a combined assessment.

Table 2: The overall rank of the highest 10 ranked rivers for micro- and macroplastic export and retention are displayed, including their fate-specific ranks. The Thames, Seyhan and Danube are also shown, as they have the highest rank for a plastic fate.

River	Overall	Export		River retention	
		Macroplastic	Microplastic	Macroplastic	Microplastic
Kurbağalı Dere (TR)	1	9	4	24	43
Vistula (PL)	2	78	14	3	5
Rhine (NL)	3	81	12	8	1
Mälaren (SE)	4	32	9	65	34
West Oder (DE)	5	93	44	6	6
Tiber (IT)	6	36	40	69	23
Weser (DE)	7	106	18	39	10
Kızılırmak (TR)	8	41	97	4	47
Seine (FR)	9	69	81	32	7
Garonne (FR)	10	129	21	86	24
Thames (UK)	18	410	1	46	9
Seyhan (TR)	26	1	502	14	65
Danube (UA)	62	176	897	1	2

Summary and future outlook

Our research shows that rivers are important temporary sinks for micro- and macroplastics, with our model estimating a reduced plastic export compared to other models. In comparing model results with similar large scale export studies, we find that modelling plastic fluxes at large scales requires a high model resolution, as small river basins contribute a large proportion to the European plastic retention and export. While absolute estimates provide a

good indication of the overall environmental burden and may profit regional management, per capita estimates for plastic export and retention facilitates policy development by allowing for a fair comparison between river basins. This also highlights the importance of choice in metrics. Furthermore, by combining export and retention scores for micro- and macroplastic to give a final score, we are able to provide a more holistic overview of the overall level of pollution of a river system. We finally emphasise the requirement of future modelling work for implementing extreme events (e.g., floods) and tidal dynamics. Both processes have the potential to significantly affect transport and retention of plastic in rivers.

Supporting Information

Additional details are provided in the Supplementary Information. S1 - Overview of the methodology used to delineate river basins; S2 - Land cover harmonisation; S3 - Outline of the quantification of plastic emission to land; S4 - Model coefficient values; S5 - Overview of the harmonised field measurements used for model calibration; S6 - Percentile classes used for Figure 5 and 6; S7 - Spearman's rank test results.

The full data-set and model code are publicly available on Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18960458). The model set-up and calculations are primarily carried out in R software (version 4.4.1). In addition, several geo-processing steps were performed using ArcGIS and QGIS. All input sources, results and code have been made open-source to promote open and FAIR science principles.

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TOC Graphic

IN REVIEW